

Metamaterial topology design with CLIP based Learning

Sourava Prasad Mishra^{1*}, Paweł Kudela²

^{1,2} Institute of Fluid-Flow Machinery, Polish Academy of Sciences, Fiszerza 14, 80-231 Gdańsk, Poland

email: ¹ smishra@imp.gda.pl, ² pk@imp.gda.pl

* Corresponding author

Abstract. Metamaterials are engineered periodic structures whose exotic properties such as acoustic bandgaps and negative Poisson's ratios are influenced by the geometry of their unit cells. Traditionally, the topological design of these lattices presents a complex challenge, particularly at higher frequencies. This process typically demands computationally expensive finite element simulations and domain expertise. Furthermore, the relationship between numerous design parameters significantly influences material properties. In this work, we propose a novel approach to forward prediction in acoustic metamaterial topology design by leveraging a Contrastive Language-Image Pre-training (CLIP) architecture that integrates computer vision and natural language processing methodologies. We develop a framework utilizing images of metamaterial topologies paired with Run-length Encoding (RLE) textual representations to predict wave propagation vectors from a joint embedding space. Evaluated on a benchmark dataset, our results demonstrate that while the visual modality captures dominant geometric features, the multimodal approach leverages complementary textual representation to provide richer semantic context.

Keywords: Acoustic Metamaterials, Acoustic Bandgaps, Forward Prediction, Topology Optimization, Multimodal Learning, CLIP.